

HOW DOES THE RACIAL BACKGROUND OF PATIENTS IMPACT
THEIR EXPERIENCE LIVING WITH CANCER

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Abstract

The population in the United States (U.S.) is composed of many races from different backgrounds and cultures, which may influence how individuals are impacted by chronic diseases. Therefore, we investigated whether the racial background of cancer patients may be correlated with their perceived mental, emotional, and physical health, quality of life as well as making positive changes after their cancer diagnosis. The data used for this study came from the Medical Expenditure Panel Survey (MEPS), which collects primary data about healthcare services from people in the U.S. We focused on its Cancer Self-Administered Questionnaire (CSAQ), which asked patients about the impact of having cancer, and its Adult Self-Administered Questionnaire (SAQ), which collected demographic information, from 2016 and 2017. A Chi-square analysis was conducted using a weighted complex survey approach. We found statistically significant racial differences in cancer patients' quality of life, positive impacts of cancer diagnosis, and physical and mental health. Specifically, while Hispanic Whites and Blacks were more likely to relate their cancer experience with positive changes, they also reported lower ratings for quality of life and physical and mental health when compared to Non-Hispanic Whites and Asians. The findings of the study highlight the variation in patients' cancer experience. Healthcare providers should be aware of these disparities to adequately care for their patients.

Introduction

The prevalence of cancer is predicted to increase over time (1). With no established cure for cancer, it is critical that healthcare professionals focus on disease management to provide the best quality of care for cancer patients. However, studies have shown that there are racial disparities in the patient care experience, particularly when it comes to ethnic minorities. An analysis of data from the National Cancer Patient Experience Survey (NCPES) conducted in England found that Blacks and Asians reported lower satisfaction and an overall less positive experience with the cancer care they received in comparison to Whites (2). In addition, a study using data from the Surveillance, Epidemiology, and End Results-Medicare Health Outcomes Survey (SEER-MHOS) of nine registries within the United States (U.S.) found that Black cancer patients had lower mental health scores and Hispanics had overall poor health-related quality of life when compared to Non-Hispanic Whites (3). Clearly, patients' racial backgrounds impact their overall care experiences. Therefore, in an effort to investigate this relationship in detail using more recent data, we utilized data from the Medical Expenditure Panel Survey (MEPS) from 2016 and 2017. The goal for this research was to examine how U.S. cancer patients' racial background might impact their perceived quality of life as well as their mental, emotional, and physical health.

Methods

Data Ascertainment

We used data from MEPS, which is an annual survey conducted by Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality to collect information on health services utilized by people in the U.S. including how often they are used as well as the costs associated with them (4). As part of MEPS, the Adult Self-Administered Questionnaire (SAQ) data was used to obtain demographic information on the subjects. Also, data from the Cancer Self-Administered Questionnaire (CSAQ) was used to capture cancer patients' experiences, including the burden of cancer, the medical care for cancer, the long-lasting effects of the disease as well as the financial impacts and employment outcomes.

Because CSAQ was only administered in 2011, 2016, and 2017 and the questions asked of participants changed in the recent versions, we focused on cancer patients who participated in 2016 and 2017. Of the 1954 patients, those who were diagnosed with only non-melanoma skin cancer and/or skin cancer of an unknown kind were excluded, along with those who did not report having health insurance and subjects who self-identified as multiracial. In addition, only subjects who answered all 9 questions of interest to our study were included. Those questions included self-ratings of quality of life, physical, emotional, and mental health as well as how often they worried their cancer may come back or get worse. We were also interested in questions related to whether having a cancer diagnosis led to any positive changes, such as if the cancer experience made them a stronger person, if they can cope better with life's challenges, if it was a reason to make positive changes in their life, and if they made healthier habits. This led to a final sample size of 1161 cancer patients, with 839 Non-Hispanic Whites, 140 Hispanic Whites, 148 Blacks, and 34 Asians.

Statistical Analysis

For the survey questions related to whether the cancer diagnosis led to any positive changes, the possible responses took a yes/no format. However, a Likert scale was used for the questions related to patients' ratings of their quality of life and physical and mental health, with possible responses of poor, fair, good, very good, and excellent. Due to small numbers for certain races, similar responses were grouped together. The subjects who answered poor were combined with those who answered fair; those who answered very good were combined with those who answered excellent. The Likert scale was also used to ask the participants regarding the occurrence of emotional problem within 7 days and if they worried their cancer may come back or get worse, with choices including never, rarely, sometimes, often, and always. Similar responses were combined for the same reason as previously mentioned. The participants who answered never were grouped with rarely, and those who responded sometimes, often, and all the time were grouped together.

The subjects were first summarized using mean and/or frequency based on age, sex, marital status, highest education level, and if they were born in the U.S. Then, Chi-square analyses were conducted to investigate whether there were any statistically significant differences in cancer patients' experiences (based on the 9 questions above) across the racial groups. To ensure the results were representative of the U.S. cancer patient population, a complex survey weighted analytic approach was taken. All analyses were done in SPSS Version 28.0, and the findings were considered statistically significant at a p-value of ≤ 0.05 .

Results

Overall, there were 1161 cancer patients, with 839 Non-Hispanic Whites, 148 Blacks, 140 Hispanic Whites, and 34 Asians. The average age of the participants was 65.32 years with most being female (59.35%) versus male (40.65%). More than half of the subjects were married (57.60%). In addition, 44.40% had at least a GED or high school diploma and 36.00% reported having a Bachelor's, Master's, or Doctorate degree. The majority of the subjects were born in the U.S. (88.72%). (Table 1)

All survey questions that asked participants whether the cancer diagnosis had any positive impact showed a statistically significant difference across the racial groups ($p < 0.001$) (Table 2). For the four questions that were asked, approximately 75-85% of Hispanic Whites and Blacks reported "yes" to their cancer diagnosis making a positive impact, while only about 55-65% of Non-Hispanic Whites and Asians reported such a response.

In addition, when participants were asked to rate their mental and physical health as well as their quality of life, there were statistically significant racial differences ($p < 0.001$) (Table 3). While 68.60% of Non-Hispanic Whites and 70.20% of Asians reported an excellent/very good rating for mental health, only 52.80% of Hispanic Whites and 49.90% of Blacks reported such ratings. This difference was also observed for physical health; while 50.70% of Non-Hispanic Whites and 49.70% Asians reported an excellent/very good rating, only 42.60% of Hispanic Whites and 33.60% of Blacks reported those ratings. Lastly, the responses regarding overall quality of life showed a similar racial pattern where 65.80% of Non-Hispanic Whites and 58.10% of Asians reported excellent/very good, while only 43.70% of Blacks and 43.20% of Hispanic Whites reported this.

There was no statistically significant difference regarding how often patients worried their cancer would come back (p-value=0.786) and their emotional health (p-value=0.252).

Discussion

Overall, our study found statistically significant differences in cancer's impact across races. Hispanic Whites and Blacks were more likely to use their cancer diagnosis to make positive changes. However, at the same time, they were also more likely to report lower ratings on physical and mental health as well as overall quality of life when compared to Non-Hispanic Whites and Asians.

One reason for why cancer could have more of a positive impact among Hispanic Whites and Blacks may have to do with cultural and religious differences. For example, certain cultures and religions may emphasize the importance of overcoming hardships and learning from the experience. A survey conducted by Pew Research Center found that three quarters of Blacks reported religion as a crucial part of their lives, and the percentage of adults who stated that they attend religious service at least once a week was highest among Blacks, followed by Latinos, Whites, and lastly Asians (5). Additionally, several studies have found that religious activities including prayer, worshiping, and reading religious texts promoted healthier well-being and positive emotions, which could help in overcoming challenges (6, 7). A study from 2020 also found that increasing religious attendance was associated decreased depressive symptoms as well as having positive well-being (8).

However, despite cancer having more of a positive impact on Hispanic Whites and Blacks, both races still reported lower quality of life and poorer physical and mental health, and this may be due to socioeconomic differences. Treatment of cancer can take a significant financial toll on patients, and there are major wealth disparities across race. According to Federal Reserve, the typical White family has eight times the wealth of the typical Black family and five times the wealth of the typical Hispanic family (9). This indicates that there is a significant

wealth gap across races, and although we excluded those lacking insurance from our analysis, there are many indirect costs associated with a cancer diagnosis that could impact overall health and quality of life. In fact, multiple studies have found that an individual's health status is directly correlated with their level of income and education, where the higher the income and education, the better the individual's health status (10, 11).

A strength of this research is the use of MEPS data, hence these results are representative of the U.S. cancer patient population. However, an important limitation is that we did not consider the patients' type of cancer or how long the patient has had their cancer, and this could play a role in quality of life since some may be actively going through treatment while others may have survived their cancer many years ago. We also did not consider the patients' medical histories, such as previous health conditions or other comorbidities. Lastly, another limitation is that all of the data were based on self-report.

In conclusion, our study identifies important racial disparities when it comes to cancer patients' experiences. Specifically, we found statistically significant differences in mental and physical health, quality of life, and if the cancer diagnosis had a positive impact across the races. When compared to Non-Hispanic Whites and Asians, Hispanic Whites and Blacks were more likely to see their cancer diagnosis as an opportunity to make positive changes, but less likely to report high ratings of physical and mental health as well as overall quality of life. These findings highlight important disparities in the cancer experience that future health professionals should be aware of so that the appropriate support is provided and patients' needs are met.

Table 1. Demographics of cancer patients included in analysis

	Mean	Standard Error
Age	65.32	0.529
	N	Weighted %
Total	1161	100.00%
Sex		
Male	472	40.90%
Female	689	59.10%
Race		
Non-Hispanic White	839	82.40%
Hispanic White	140	7.50%
Black	148	7.50%
Asian	34	2.60%
Marital Status		
Never Married	101	7.70%
Married	630	57.60%
Widowed, Divorced, or Separated	430	34.60%
Highest Education Level		
No Degree	153	9.20%
GED or High School Diploma	530	44.40%
Bachelor's, Master's, or Doctorate	363	36.00%
Other	112	10.10%
Don't Know / Refused	3	0.20%
Born in U.S.		
Yes	1030	91.90%
No	131	8.10%

Table 2. Analyses of cancer having a positive impact on patients by racial group

	NON-HISPANIC WHITE		HISPANIC WHITE		BLACK		ASIAN		P-Value
	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	
MADE A STRONGER PERSON									<0.001
Yes	537	63.90%	112	82.00%	122	85.00%	21	61.90%	
No	302	36.10%	28	18.00%	26	15.00%	13	38.10%	
COPE BETTER WITH CHALLENGES									<0.001
Yes	511	58.70%	111	81.20%	116	82.80%	23	65.00%	
No	328	41.30%	29	18.80%	32	17.20%	11	35.00%	
REASON FOR POSITIVE CHANGES									<0.001
Yes	448	53.80%	108	77.90%	109	80.40%	20	59.30%	
No	391	46.20%	32	22.10%	39	19.60%	14	40.70%	
MADE HEALTHIER HABITS									<0.001
Yes	478	57.70%	109	82.10%	109	78.20%	23	65.10%	
No	361	42.30%	31	17.90%	39	21.80%	11	34.90%	

Table 3. Analyses for mental, physical, emotional health, cancer concern and overall quality of life ratings by race

	NON-HISPANIC WHITE		HISPANIC WHITE		BLACK		ASIAN		P-Value
	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	N	Weight %	
WORRY CANCER COME BACK									0.786
Never/Rarely	406	47.10%	57	46.40%	67	41.40%	18	48.90%	
Sometimes/Often/All the Time	433	52.90%	83	53.60%	81	58.60%	16	51.10%	
RATE MENTAL HEALTH									0.004
Excellent/ Very Good	564	68.60%	61	52.80%	75	49.90%	21	70.20%	
Good	174	20.50%	45	30.70%	45	32.00%	9	20.20%	
Fair/ Poor	101	10.80%	34	16.50%	28	18.10%	4	9.60%	
EMOTIONAL PROBLEM IN 7 DAYS									0.252
Never/Rarely	557	67.50%	73	59.30%	93	59.10%	22	65.30%	
Sometimes/Often/Always	282	32.50%	67	40.70%	55	40.90%	12	34.70%	
RATE PHYSICAL HEALTH									0.014
Excellent/ Very Good	401	50.70%	45	42.60%	42	33.60%	15	49.70%	
Good	261	29.00%	37	25.50%	56	33.60%	9	21.30%	
Fair/ Poor	177	20.30%	58	31.90%	50	32.80%	10	28.90%	
RATE QUALITY OF LIFE									<0.001
Excellent/ Very Good	530	65.80%	46	43.20%	62	43.70%	18	58.10%	
Good	197	21.80%	54	36.30%	54	35.00%	9	18.50%	
Fair/ Poor	112	12.40%	40	20.50%	32	21.30%	7	23.40%	

References

- 1) Sung, H., Ferlay, J., Siegel, R. L., Laversanne, M., Soerjomataram, I., Jemal, A., & Bray, F. (2021). Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 71(3), 209–249. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.3322/caac.21660>
- 2) Pinder, R. J., Ferguson, J., & Møller, H. (2016). Minority ethnicity patient satisfaction and experience: results of the National Cancer Patient Experience Survey in England. *BMJ Open*, 6(6), e011938.
- 3) Rincon, M. A., Smith, A. W., Yu, M., & Kent, E. E. (2020). Trends in racial/ethnic disparity of health-related quality of life in older adults with and without cancer (1998–2012). *Cancer Epidemiology Biomarkers & Prevention*, 29(6), 1188–1195.
- 4) Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (n.d.). Medical Expenditure Panel Survey Home. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from <https://www.meps.ahrq.gov/mepsweb/>
- 5) Pew Research Center. (2015). America's changing religious landscape. <https://www.pewforum.org/2015/05/12/americas-changing-religious-landscape>
- 6) Taylor, R. J., Chatters, L. M., & Levin, J. (2004). Religion in the lives of African Americans: Social, psychological, and health perspectives. Sage Publications.
- 7) Chatters, L. M. (2000). Religion and health: Public health research and practice. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 21, 335–367. doi:10.1146/annurev.publhealth.21.1.335
- 8) Nguyen A. W. (2020). Religion and mental health in racial and ethnic minority populations: A review of the literature. *Innovation in Aging*, 4(5), igaa035.
- 9) Bhutta, N., Chang, A. C., Dettling, L. J., & Joanne W. Hsu with assistance from Julia Hewitt. (n.d.). Disparities in wealth by race and ethnicity in the 2019 survey of Consumer Finances. The Fed - Disparities in Wealth by Race and Ethnicity in the 2019 Survey of Consumer Finances. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from <https://www.federalreserve.gov/econres/notes/feds-notes/disparities-in-wealth-by-race-and-ethnicity-in-the-2019-survey-of-consumer-finances-20200928.htm>
- 10) Bonnar, K., & McCarthy, M. (2012). Health Related Quality of Life in a Rural Area with Low Racial/Ethnic Density. *Journal of Community Health*, 37(1), 96–104. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1007/s10900-011-9422-2>
- 11) Wilkinson, R. G., & Pickett, K. E. (2008). Income inequality and socioeconomic gradients in mortality. *American Journal of Public Health*, 98, 699–704.

12) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022, April 27). Cancer. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Retrieved May 12, 2022, from <https://www.cdc.gov/chronicdisease/resources/publications/facts>